

Electrochemical Reduction of Morin at DME

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The electrochemical behaviour of Morin (5,7,2',4'-tetrahydroxyflavonol) is described on the basis of polarographic studies in BR buffers (pH 6.0-10.6) containing 25 and 50% each of ethanol, acetonitrile and dimethylformamide and in sodium hydroxide solutions. The effect of pH, solvent composition and height of the mercury reservoir on electrode reaction is discussed. The process is irreversible and a continuous negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ is observed from pH 6.0-10.6 in BR buffers.

THE electrochemical behaviour of flavonoids at dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) over a wide range of pH has been studied earlier¹⁻⁷ and quantitative conclusions were drawn regarding the ease of reduction in relation to substituent groups. Based on the above experiments, the depolarizing centre in flavone molecule was found to be the heterocyclic oxygen or the carbonyl group depending on the pH of the medium.

Morin belongs to the flavonol group. In general, these classes of compounds are the constituents of natural pigments which are useful colouring materials. The present work deals with the polarographic study of morin (5,7,2',4'-tetrahydroxyflavonol) in BR buffer (pH 6.0-10.6). The investigation has been carried out in 25 and 50% ethanol, acetonitrile or dimethylformamide solutions, respectively at different heights of the mercury reservoir. Polarography of Morin has also been carried out in sodium hydroxide solution of varying concentration (0.10, 0.25, 0.50 and 1.00 N). Measurements of the title compound was made at 0.001 M concentration and at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Morin (I) had not been investigated previously. Preliminary studies revealed that the flavonols undergo a 2-electron transfer reduction wave¹. A detailed account of the studies is reported in this paper. The mechanism of the two electron reduction process at d.m.e. has been proposed and discussed. The proposed mechanism infers the formation of 3,4,5,7,2',4'-hexahydroxyflavene (V).

were prepared from these. Britton and Robinson buffers⁸ in pH range of 6.0-10.6 was used. All solvents and reagents were of analytical grade. Solvents were purified by standard methods⁹.

Apparatus :

An automatic pen recording polarograph, Polariter PO 4 49418, Copenhagen NV was used. The reference electrode cell was an aqueous saturated NaCl calomel electrode (SCE). Dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) was utilized as working electrode. Toshniwal CL 43 pH meter with a combined glass electrode was used for pH measurements. The electrolysis was carried out in a H-cell in conjunction with agar-agar plug saturated with NaCl. Sargent capillary used has the characteristic of $m = 1.927 \text{ mg sec}^{-1}$ and $t = 4.5 \text{ sec/drop}$. Unless otherwise specified, the experiments were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The samples were deaerated by bubbling pressurized purified nitrogen gas for 15 min. The nitrogen gas was previously circulated through a thermostatic recipient containing the solution of the sample without electroactive agent.

The $E_{1/2}$ values were measured against the SCE. The polarographic runs were made in ethanol, acetonitrile and dimethylformamide-BR buffer mixtures and sodium hydroxide solutions.

The study was carried out at pH 6.0, 8.0 and 10.6. All polarograms were recorded at two percentages

Experimental

Materials :

0.05 M Morin (Eastman) and 1.0 N sodium hydroxide (SM), were used. More diluted solutions

of solvents (25 and 50%) and at three heights of the mercury reservoir (40, 50 and 60 cm). In sodium hydroxide solution the study was carried out in 0.10, 0.25, 0.50 and 1.00 N NaOH media.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF THE REDUCTION OF MORIN (0.001 M) IN ETHANOL-BR BUFFER

Ethanol (%)	pH	Height of the mercury reservoir (cm)								
		40			50			60		
		i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Slope (V)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Slope (V)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Slope (V)
25	6.0	0.4500	1.190	0.1666	0.5025	1.192	0.1739	0.5925	1.191	0.1869
	8.0	0.4950	1.200	0.1639	0.5550	1.194	0.1709	0.5700	1.193	0.1666
	10.6	0.5400	1.201	0.1538	0.5550	1.196	0.1666	0.7425	1.194	0.1538
50	6.0	0.7425	1.301	0.1574	0.8790	1.305	0.1639	0.9825	1.306	0.1739
	8.0	0.3090	1.303	0.1234	0.3825	1.306	0.1538	0.4950	1.308	0.1538
	10.6	0.5400	1.305	0.1212	0.5850	1.307	0.1311	0.7170	1.309	0.1379

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF THE REDUCTION OF MORIN (0.001 M) IN ACETONITRILE-BR BUFFER

Acetonitrile (%)	pH	Height of the mercury reservoir (cm)								
		40			50			60		
		i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Slope (V)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Slope (V)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Slope (V)
25	6.0	0.6360	1.290	0.1769	0.7320	1.285	0.1724	0.7680	1.292	0.1785
	8.0	0.4860	1.305	0.1754	0.5100	1.295	0.1709	0.5370	1.293	0.1739
	10.6	0.3780	1.313	0.1739	0.3900	1.312	0.1694	0.4140	1.310	0.1709
50	6.0	0.7650	1.310	0.1739	0.9450	1.308	0.1801	0.9750	1.305	0.1694
	8.0	0.7260	1.312	0.1709	0.9300	1.310	0.1785	1.0380	1.309	0.1666
	10.6	0.4380	1.314	0.1639	0.4330	1.313	0.1639	0.5280	1.312	0.1538

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF THE REDUCTION OF MORIN (0.001 M) IN DIMETHYLFORMAMIDE-BR BUFFER

Dimethylformamide (%)	pH	Height of the mercury reservoir (cm)								
		40			50			60		
		i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Slope (V)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Slope (V)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Slope (V)
25	6.0	0.3900	1.307	0.2380	0.4500	1.302	0.2352	0.4950	1.301	0.2597
	8.0	0.5400	1.309	0.2352	0.6030	1.303	0.2162	0.6540	1.302	0.2127
	10.6	0.5160	1.312	0.2061	0.5550	1.306	0.2000	0.5850	1.304	0.2051
50	6.0	0.4140	1.385	0.2234	0.4500	1.390	0.2352	0.5040	1.392	0.2597
	8.0	0.4350	1.388	0.2222	0.5100	1.396	0.2234	0.5550	1.399	0.2499
	10.6	0.4290	1.390	0.2127	0.4890	1.397	0.2222	0.5100	1.407	0.2352

TABLE 4—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF THE REDUCTION OF MORIN (0.001 M) IN NaOH (0.1-1.0 N)

Concentration of NaOH (N)	pH	Height of the mercury reservoir (cm)								
		40			50			60		
		i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Slope (V)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Slope (V)	i_d (μ A)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	Slope (V)
1.00	6.0	0.1020	1.040	0.1315	0.1065	1.065	0.1159	0.1110	1.070	0.1098
0.50	6.0	0.2205	1.270	0.1818	0.2400	1.285	0.3636	0.2640	1.230	0.3671
0.25	6.0	0.1875	1.263	0.2758	0.1950	1.230	0.3225	0.2325	1.225	0.3478
0.10	6.0	0.1200	1.215	0.1666	0.1560	1.184	0.1515	0.1590	1.217	0.2352

Results and Discussion

Polarographic behaviour of Morin :

A well defined single step reduction of Morin is observed when it is reduced at d.m.e. Thus, the compound under investigation gave a single two electron reduction wave over the pH range 6.0-10.6 and also in NaOH solutions. The variation of i_d , $E_{1/2}$ and the slope with pH, height of mercury

column and percentages of the solvents for all the three solvents and NaOH solutions are summarised in Tables 1-4. The limiting current of these waves were found to be diffusion controlled as evident from the linear plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$. The nature of the waves was found to be irreversible as evinced by log plots shifts in $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential with increasing pH.

Effect of pH :

By polarographic data only one reduction wave is observed for Morin over the pH range 6.0-10.6 in all the three solvents studied. The half wave potential was found to be pH dependent and shifted linearly towards more negative potential with increase in pH (Fig. 1). However, the slope decreased slightly with

Fig. 1. Plots of $-E_{1/2}$ vs pH for Morin in (a) ethanol-BR buffer, (b) acetonitrile-BR buffer, (c) dimethyl formamide-BR buffer; (—) 25%, (---) 50% of solvent at \circ , 40 cm; Δ , 50 cm and \square , 60 cm of Hg height.

Fig. 2. Plots of $-E_{1/2}$ vs Hg height for Morin in (a) ethanol-BR buffer, (b) acetonitrile-BR buffer, (c) dimethyl formamide-BR buffer; (—) 25% and (---) 50% of solvent at pH 6.0, \circ ; 8.0, Δ and 10.6, \square .

increase in pH. The pH dependent nature of $E_{1/2}$ indicated the participation of protons in the reduction and this fact obviously led to the conclusion that the fast proton transfer precedes the main electrode process (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Effect of solvent composition :

The data on the variation of $E_{1/2}$ and i_d with increase in the percentages of ethanol, acetonitrile and dimethylformamide from 25 to 50% shows that $E_{1/2}$ shifts towards more negative potential simultaneously with increase in the percentage of the solvents. The $E_{1/2}$ is shifted towards negative direction in the order $\text{EtOH} < \text{AcN} < \text{DMF}$.

There are several factors with regards to solvent composition which singly or collectively would affect the electrode process. Viscosity of the organic solvent and, solvation of the electroactive species seems to be the more operative factors. Both these factors sharply lower the rate of protonation and, therefore, lead to a shift in $E_{1/2}$ of the reduction wave towards negative potential where protonation precedes the electron transfer.

Effect of the height of the mercury reservoir :

In the present observations, in cases when the amount of solvent was 25%, the $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards positive directions in all the cases with increasing Hg height, but with 50% solvent, the $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative direction with increasing Hg height. However, with 50% acetonitrile the $E_{1/2}$ shifted to the positive direction (Fig. 2). In all the three solvents and in NaOH solutions i_d increased with increasing height of the mercury column.

Effect of NaOH concentration :

Polarograms of Morin were studied at different concentration of NaOH viz. 0.10, 0.25, 0.50 and 1.00 N NaOH media. At all the concentrations the i_d increased with increasing height of Hg column. Though the i_d in 1.00 N NaOH solution increased with increasing height of Hg column, the slope decreased slightly. In other concentrations, $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards positive direction with increasing Hg height.

On the basis of the fact that a two electron reduction wave was obtained in all the above con-

ditions, the above reduction mechanism at the electrode is proposed (Scheme 1).

The electrode process therefore could be considered to be a mono anion radical (II) formation by one electron addition followed by protonation of the ionic radical. The uptake of the second electron occurs with no further requirement of activation energy, so that only a single polarographic wave is observed. It is expected that further protonation of the anion radical (IV) in the media affords the 3,4,5,7,2,4'-hexahydroxy flavene (V).

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